

THE LASANOD WAR IS MORE SERIOUS THAN WE THINK: THE INFLUENCE AND CONSEQUENCES OF EXTERNAL ACTORS

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Dedication

This article is dedicated to all free-thinking individuals who value Somaliland's peace, stability, and unity.

Disclaimer

Nobody paid him to write this article. His heart and love for his country drove him to write and devote tens of hours of his precious time. He wasn't thirsty, tired, or worried while he was writing. However, now that he's publicised it, he's sorry that he thought it would be a good idea to include a disclaimer. He is not happy to say this, but he believes it is important to state: "I have no intention of causing harm to my state, Somaliland, or criticising H.E. President Muse Bihi and his government or anyone else, but I am aware I am aware that our people have not yet adopted the tolerance of expressing different thoughts,. However, pleasing everyone is impossible, so I resolved to do everything in my power to save my country, which is more valuable than anything else. To remain silent about what I believe to be the truth in order to save the nation because I am afraid of being harmed by the government or others is disappointing and makes me see myself as foolish, which my heart has never accepted. I believe that anyone who values their country above all else will appreciate this article."

The Lasanod War Is More Serious Than We Think: The Influence and Consequences of External Actors

Introduction

Somaliland's past and present images are diametrically opposed. Somaliland's previous image was one of peace, political stability, social, economic, and political development, and a vision of a beautiful national future, whereas its current image is one of lethal political conflict and formless politics, economic collapse, social division, and war. The war in Lasanod is a clear example of how Somaliland is falling apart. It is the first of several great disasters that will likely cause Somaliland to collapse unless the government adopts new strategies and changes its response to the Lasanod crisis and opposition.

The aim of this article is to look into the external factors that have contributed to the ongoing conflict in Lasanod between the Somaliland army and the Dhulbahante clan forces, also known as SSC, which reside in the eastern Somaliland regions of Sool, Sanaag, and Ayn, by answering the question, "What are the external factors that cause the Lasanod war and what are their consequences on Somaliland's statehood?" Because the local perspective and analysis of Somaliland's political commentators are all about domestic factors, as if Somaliland were an island cut off from global politics, the focus is to study if there are external factors and how they can contribute to the war.

As a result, one of the two categories of reasons for the Lasanod War will be discussed in this article, as will the consequences if the government does not change its political behavior. This problem is caused by two types of factors: external and internal political factors. It will examine external factors, which are classified into two types: The first is the legacy of colonialism left by the country's political culture, and the second is a shift in the international political system.

Somaliland political development and fluctuation

Some background

Somaliland is an unrecognized country, so its main goal for the past 30 years has been to gain recognition, and the only thing it was selling was peace, stability, and democracy in order to gain international recognition as a sovereign state. It is a very fragile state with a very weak governments that a number of rival Somali clans built under the national charter of traditional

leaders. Until 2003, the government was based on clan bases, with traditional clan leaders playing a significant role in politics and the government system in order to determine who would lead the country. Nonetheless, after the first one-man, one-vote election in 2003, when ex-President HE. Dahir Rayale Kahin was elected as president, it appeared that a political transition had occurred for two reasons: first, the elected president was not from the largest clan, which was previously thought to be impossible in Somali society due to the clan system. Second, in comparison to reality, the perception of democracy appeared to be very positive. People felt as if they were going to heaven for the first election because the current generation has never witnessed a democratic election in their country. This was very interesting, and it was expected that clan-based politics would pass and lead to better politics, but it actually got worse for two reasons.

Except for HE. Abdirahman Ahmed Ali (Tour), who resigned, and HE. Haji Mohamed Ibrahim Egal, who through clan based elections, HE. Dahir Rayale Kahin, HE. Ahmed Mohamed M. Silanyo, and until HE. Muse Bihi came to power, three presidential elections were held since the republic's inception. Somaliland's political situation took an unexpected turn when it adopted a multi-party democratic system. To begin with, everything in politics has returned to the clan system in a worse way than in the indirect election, when elected parliament members by traditional elders were used to elect the president. All political parties have evolved into clans that have banded together and joined forces to win elections over other clans. Following the election, governments shift to those who are unkind to the state's property and social solidarity, and do not consider anyone other than the tribe that won the election. As a result, political stakeholder groups were divided into two categories: those who rule from ally clans and those who oppose them. Second, while governments differed, any government formed through elections appeared to violate the social contract. Everything changed, and instead of acting in accordance with the wishes of the general public and satisfying the majority of clans through power sharing, the governments behaved like a dictatorship.

Despite political conflicts and challenges, Somaliland's society has always maintained hope, despite the country's slow development. When compared to the challenges and political conflicts that existed prior to President Muse Bihi Abdi's election in 2017, there has been greater progress in the development of hope and economic, political, and social cohesion. However, following his inauguration, the country faced greater and more dangerous challenges as well as more complex political conflicts than in the past.

Bihi began his reign with promising intentions, but his policies led to social dissatisfaction later on. He began to demolish the Rainbow Umbrella, a coalition of clans that was either behind his success or made it possible for him to win the presidential election. He severed ties with close members of his political party, some of whom were popular and astute campaigners for his election, including Mohamud Hashi, a powerful former minister in President Siylanyo's government. Unlike previous presidents, he did not appear to listen to anyone and distanced himself from Somaliland's "political culture web," including traditional leaders, including those from his own tribe, some of whom he attempted to arrest, such as his own sultan, sultan Hassan sultan Abdirahman; some of them were arrested, such as sultan Ade Gude, after they tried to oppose him, and he felt that they were provoking the people against him. The most dangerous issue arose when President Muse failed to honour an agreement signed by his predecessor's government with Professor Ali Khalif Galaid, who was leading Khatumo-SSC 2017, the rebel fighting in the Sool region. The agreement, which aimed to end the conflict between the government and the rebels while also avoiding a future conflict, stipulated that the constitution be reopened in order to find a power sharing system based on equality and justice.

By ignoring traditional leaders, religious scholars, and the educated, he completely altered the way former presidents used to resolve political disagreements when he said that everything should be regarded according to the constitution. He fell silent, ignoring public yelling, opposition criticism, and politicians' threatening speeches. He barred access to all hidden powers that were not part of the government system. He attempted to halt the government's illegal payments. He prohibited giving money to those who had received bribes from previous administrations while not part of the system, such as traditional leaders and former politicians who served in those administrations. As a result, the populace provoked the president, who received nicknames like "Lock" for stopping illegal payments.

Since Muse Bihi's 5-year term ended and the senate, which extended their term by five years on its own after their 5-year term ended, extended Muse Bihi's term by two years in 2022, the political conflict between the opposition and the government and social fragmentation into clans have become the worst Somaliland has ever faced. As a result, the opposition has staged several protests in Somaliland, including in Hargeisa and Burao, against President Muse Bihi and his government, each with a different goal. The crowds from Burao and Hargeisa were protesting the extension of Bihi's term after his five-year term expired. There were other protests before those mentioned against him when he took office and after the success of his presidential election. Lasanod's protest was different, and it was against a series of assassination murders that had

occurred in the city over the previous 15 years. Protesters claimed that since the Somaliland government took control of the region, more than 130 assassinations have occurred, and it is strange that no one has been arrested for at least one of the murders.

The government denied that figure, claiming it was closer to 40 assassinations, and some of the criminals were apprehended despite the lack of evidence presented to the public. The most recent protest in Lasanod, on the other hand, has fundamentally altered the political climate and perception of the country's future because it devolved into a conflict between government forces and Khatumo-SSC militias from the local Dhulbahante clan, led by traditional leaders. The clan's traditional leaders led the region's rebel leader, who declared in a meeting that the regions of Sool, Sanaag, and Ain, as they put it, do not recognise Somaliland, that their land belongs to Somalia, and that Somaliland and Somalia will never be separated.

The government surprised everyone by allowing traditional leaders, some of whom had been exiled from the country for the previous 15 years, to enter Lasanod to host a large meeting for the entire clan of elders, despite government officials claiming it was to avoid further problems and they expected a good return from the elders. The traditional leaders entered Lasanod with the Somalia national flag, which was prohibited in this country, which surprised the public. Furthermore, before entering Lasanod, these traditional leaders articulated their opposition to the Somaliland state by claiming that they never recognised Somaliland and were instead a part of Somalia. They also stated that the Somaliland force in the region should leave. Because of the government's stance on this issue, a fierce war has erupted, with deaths and injuries on both sides, as well as the displacement of civilians living in Lasanod.

The majority of the region's prominent politicians have sided with their people. Among the politicians was Somaliland's Speaker of the House of Representatives, Abdirisak Khalif, who accused the government of genocide in the region, the chairmen of the political associations Wabari and SPP, Abdirizak Atash and Saleban Xaglotosiye, who resigned from their positions as chairmen of their political associations, which were expected to compete to be one of the state's three political parties in the next ten years, and Because of the resignations of the two chairpersons, the two political organizations have left the political arena. The withdrawal of these two men from the political arena and the kicking of political organizations is a blow to Somaliland's political image because, in the last 20 years, the politics of Somaliland has been one-sided and all three political parties have been chaired by the 'Middle clan' in Somaliland,

which is the largest clan; therefore, it was important for the beauty of Somaliland's political image that at least one of the political parties should be from the other two second-largest clans in the country.

The Causes and Consequences of External Actors

Given the situation it is in or its background, this country is completely irrational and intolerant of entering a war, whether external or internal, for two reasons: first, the principles it established and the history it experienced, such as its claims to be remedial secessionist; and second, the status quo and what it was envisioning, as it is unrecognised and eager to gain recognition from the international community as a sovereign state. In theory, Somaliland was founded on the premise that Somalilanders regained their independence from Somalia on May 18, 1991. Nonetheless, that argument has not worked in Somaliland's 30 years of existence. However, the people who founded Somaliland, who did so from the bottom of their hearts, do not disagree with the argument that the government of Somalia committed genocide against them, so they established a separate country called Somaliland from Somalia.

However, Somaliland's current government is at odds with one of its clans. Although the government denied it, this clan, like Somaliland, claims that the Somaliland government oppressed them and committed genocide against them, arguing that the Somaliland government is a threat to their existence. They claim that during Somaliland's 15-year rule, their elites were murdered in a conspiracy, and 130 people were killed, with the government accused of being behind it. They claim that when they protested against the last person killed in December 2022, demanding that the government bring the person responsible for the murder to justice, the government responded by shooting and killing 19 unarmed protestors. This claim has spread to every corner of the globe.

The purpose of this article is not to recount what occurred, but to answer a question: if there was a planned murder, it used to happen, but the problem has never been as severe as it is now. If there is a war, it is not the first between the government of Somaliland and the local people, but the problem has never been as severe as it is now. What is the current cause of the issue becoming so serious that Somaliland's reputation, economy, and internal and external politics have been harmed? It divided reason into two categories: external precipitating causes and

internal deep causes. It is, however, investigating the external causes and consequences of the war in Lasanod.

The Causes and Consequences of the Lasanod War

The ongoing war in Lasanod, Somaliland's worst event, has altered the country's image and direction, as well as cast doubt on the country's future existence. There are two causes: the first is the nation's colonial-era political culture. It is the result of a colonial legacy that has influenced society's relationship with the modern state, and it involves several issues, four of which will be discussed: arbitrarily drawn borders, foreign political ideologies, very weak institutions, and political agents (politicians who act as middlemen). The second cause is a shift in the global political system, and it is not surprising to say that the Lasanod War has been one of the world's political events since 2017, when the US world order began to face potential peer competitors. In other words, the Lasanod War represents a shift in the international political system from a unipolar to a multipolar system, with the decline of US imperialism and the rise of new emerging great powers such as China and Russia.

Colonial Legacy: Deep Cause Factors Contributed to the War in Lasanod

The Lasanod War stems from a disagreement over colonial boundaries. Dhulbanhante residents argued that they do not recognize or are not a part of Somaliland and oppose any attempt to separate Somalia and Somaliland, but they are a part of Somalia. According to the Somaliland government, it is protecting its colonial border with British Somaliland and must maintain territorial integrity, while articulating that Somalia is Italian colonial territory, and thus Somaliland and Somalia are two countries.

This disagreement arose following the assassination of an opposition politician named Abdifatah Abdullahi Abdi 'Hadrawi on December 26, 2023, in Lasanod by an unknown gunman. Following the killing, angry residents gathered and protested in the city's main streets, where they clashed with Somaliland government forces, killing approximately 20 civilians, though the government claimed it was less than 20. Following that, the local people's argument, which was that the government should bring the person who killed Hadrawi to our hands, changed into declaring that they are not part of Somaliland but of Somalia, and the civil uprising turned into an armed one, resulting in a large war between Somaliland government forces and rebels formed in that region. According to Phil Miller, the war killed 150 people

and displaced 200,000 on March 8, 2023, and it continues to this day, on April 12, 2023, when this article is being written.

This event, like many others in Africa, is the result of colonial legacies. The relationship between what is known as the modern state and its society is very poor due to a number of issues, four of which I will mention: Arbitrary borders, foreign political ideologies, very weak institutions, and political agents (politicians who are middlemen).

The post-colonial state is an artificial state defined by colonial territories imposed on Somali society against its will by colonialists. As a result, the postcolonial state has never received social legitimacy. There is ample evidence for this, including the fact that Somalia is one of only two states that has never recognized African colonial borders. Nonetheless, unlike Somalia, Somaliland has recognized the colonial border between Somaliland and Somalia as well as the borders between Somalia and Kenya, Somalia and Ethiopia, and Somaliland and Ethiopia in order to gain international recognition as a sovereign state from Somalia.

The two warring sides, the rebels, and the government forces, are dying due to a colonial border that was not marked with either of their choices by colonialism. People of the same ethnicity were divided into different territories by colonial borders, such as the Somalis, who were divided into five territories, two of which were scattered across Ethiopia and Kenya. Borders have also become a place to bring people of different ethnicities together by separating them from their own people of the same ethnicity; Tanzania, for example, has 200 ethnic groups, each with its own language, culture, and religion.

As a result, interstate and intrastate conflicts have become common in Africa, contributing to the continent's political, economic, and social problems. For example, it is what caused Ethiopia and Somalia to fight in 1977 over the Somali land of Hawd and the reserve area, which was handed over to Ethiopia by the British in 1954; Kenya and Somalia in the Somali region of Kenya, known as the NFD; Ethiopia and Eritrea over Badame; Sudan, Ethiopia, and Kenya over the Elemi Triangle; Kenya and Somalia over the Naraw Triangle in the Indian Ocean; Chana and the Ivory Coast over an Atlantic Ocean border; and Tanzania and Kenya over a border in Lake Malawi.

The colonial border also causes conflict within countries; for example, Ethiopia and the ONLF from the Somali region fighting to separate from the rest of the country prior to the 2016

revolution; Sudan and the SPLA rebellion that resulted in the division of Sudan into two countries, namely South Sudan and Sudan; Mali and the English-speaking separatist group in the country's north in 2017; and many others.

The context of the war between the Somaliland government, led by Muse Bihi Abdi, and the SSC rebels from the eastern regions, on the other hand, is obviously different from the case in which Somaliland was established. And the reason for this is that when SNM rebels from the northern regions of Somalia, who were fighting against Siad Bare's rule, declared the Republic of Somaliland and separated from the rest of Somalia after the Siad Barre regime was toppled, their argument was based on the fact that they were British colonial territory and took their independence from the UK on June 26, 1960, thus regaining their independence that they had lost after they united with Somalia on July 1, 1960.

On the other hand, SSC's argument is not based on the colonial territory; they have an uncolonized outlook and are clearly opposed to colonial borders. They claim that they do not recognize the British-drawn border and that they are not part of Somaliland, but rather of Somalia. Colonial borders create unfinished conflict because colonial territories in African countries are based on colonial views and strategic interests rather than the inhabitant's choice.

Colonialism not only left Africa with artificial territories that hampered Somaliland's and the continent's political, economic, and social development, which had its origins in the pre-colonial era and has the potential to become an alternative civilization on this planet today, but it also forced Africa to swallow a foreign political ideology, such as artificial democracy (a democracy that does not produce desirable products).

Democracy, a foreign and irrelevant political system, has replaced and removed the Somali traditional political system. This means that a political system of government that was appropriate for the life of this society, stemming from the organ of the society and rooted in the social system that had been developing since their inception and descended from their ancestors, has been replaced by a foreign system of government based on foreign culture and ideologies that do not share the same circumstances, religion, color, culture, and climate. As a result, political confusion has resulted in the formation of a hybrid system comprised of a traditional political system and a foreign political system (travesty democracy).

It is illegitimate for several reasons, the first being that it is a void democracy devoid of democratic principles such as citizen participation, equality, political tolerance, accountability, and transparency. Because democracy arose from individualism, and the Somaliland people are collectivist, the majority of voters, who are groups of competing clans made up of 99% of the unaware members of ordinary society, do not vote or participate in politics as citizens but as clan protectors. As a result, it appears that a group of winning clans owns the government following the election because the group of clans that won the election defeated other groups of clans. It is uncommon to see someone vote solely for the well-being of the state, regardless of how their candidate, whoever he may be, comes to power.

It should come as no surprise that equality will never be possible. Following the election, a populist political system is established that benefits some clans while alienating others. The ruling politicians and their clans all share political positions, job opportunities, and projects. Even though clans that lost elections are politically involved and given lower positions, they do not receive justice or equality. Worse, political tolerance has declined, making it very easy to oppress workers and politicians from clans that lost elections. The government appoints new civil servants to replace those from the clans that were defeated in the elections.

There is no one to hold accountable. Despite the fact that the public elects both the president and the parliament, and the parliament approves the members of the president's cabinet, the executive branch dominates the legislative and judicial branches of government. As a result, like the previous governments, the executive acts like a dictatorship, creating a connected and highly organized system of corruption in which no one has been arrested for corruption in Somaliland's 30 years except for political individuals who were specifically targeted.

In general, there is no transparency. Except for false reports and misleading information released by the heads of ineffective institutions, no one knows or has any idea what the government is doing or how it is doing it. Because of a lack of institutions, all of the above democratic principles cannot exist. Somaliland's institutions are nothing more than skeletons of buildings, desks, chairs, and computers staffed by innocent, unaware, and oppressed workers. Instead of working in an organization with policies, procedures, rules, and regulations, an individual or group of people with similar interests decides everything, and when they leave, they take all the information with them. This means that each new government begins from scratch.

Second, democracy is inapplicable to this state. Despite the fact that Somaliland's democracy is hollow, personalist politics and Western interference in Somali culture and Islamic religion exist. This occurs in two ways: the first is the formation and establishment of a political system that does not fully represent society and is based on appeasement and tolerance of the spread of US values and liberalism's principles. One example is the government's close relationship with the Cultural Centre of Hargeisa, whose activities always enrage religious and traditional leaders as well as the majority of the society because it is accused of spreading liberal values such as homogenous sexuality (gays and lesbians) and westernizing the society.

Another case in point is the arrest of journalist, mullah, and philanthropist Abdimalik Coldon. This man was arrested after accusing a foreign American man and a Nigerian woman, Pastor Joy Essa, of violating the culture and religion of the state. He accused the man, a famous American gay, of spreading hemorrhagic sexuality at Barwaqo School and a Nigerian woman of spreading Christianity at the same school, while the government accused him of inciting people to rebel against the government and ordering his arrest.

Another issue that did not come to the people's will was the escape of Sheikh Aden Sune from the country. Sheikh Aden Sune was an unarmed radical mullah whose speeches focused on raising public awareness and preventing acts against Islamic culture and religion in society. He opposed the spread of liberal principles pushed by the United States; his actions did not bother the people, but they were something that the government could not tolerate because it was influenced by foreign intervention and considered itself to be a liberal democracy, as the president stated several times.

Although mosques were used to promote individual interests and disseminate political views that may have caused public confusion, it was also unprecedented for the government to tell mosques what they should and should not do. The government has issued guidelines for mosques to follow, such as not allowing the mosque's speaker's voice to be heard outside except when calling the prayer (adaan). All of the examples of things the government has done mentioned above lack legitimacy, and the government is using coercion instead of legitimacy. As a result, when the government takes such actions, it loses legitimacy and is perceived as an external government. As a result, people despise the government, and opposition is fierce.

Political figures are agents and middlemen between the state and the West. Politics has become a business, and the politician sees it as such. As a result, the politician personalises the

institution in order to further his interests. His preferences, love, and hatred are what dictate everything. He is acting in his own best interests, even if it is against national interests. They act like colonialists from the colonial era, and no one can question them except foreign donors and superpowers.

Because the state is defined solely by colonial territory, regardless of the wishes of the people who own the land, and because the political system is based on colonial ideology and the politicians are pro-colonialism, the legitimacy of the state and government is diminished. The reliance of a society on Islamic courts run by religious leaders and traditional customary rule by traditional leaders is evidence of this. The Lasanod War, led by traditional leaders, is the best example of how this modern colonial state is designed to be unrepresentative of its people. The people of Lasanod are fighting as a clan against the state and government of Somaliland. Tradition, which is led by traditional leaders, is what unites them to fight against the Muse's government. They believe that Somaliland is a threat to their existence and that they must fight it.

When you look closely, what is fighting against the government is not the people, but the traditional leaders, who are very upset with President Muse Bihi's government, and the reason is Muse Bihi's miscalculation of the traditional leaders' traditional power. Apart from the 5 years of Muse Bihi, the traditional leaders who have been invisible governments under the Somaliland government have played a role in the governance of the Somaliland governments in the 30 years of Somaliland's existence. They not only used to solve problems among their clans but also any political conflict between governments and their opponents; after all, they are the ones who established Somaliland. As a result, governments have respected, welcomed, and rewarded them; however, President Muse disagrees. President Muse, on the other hand, has confronted the traditional elders, who are more powerful and have more legitimacy in Somali society than him because he is part of the colonial system, as we discussed.

President Bihi's clash with the traditional leader has strained relations between President Muse's government and the tribes. It also caused the traditional leaders' role in resolving political disputes to cease, and instead, the opposition and traditional leaders share the same vision. The traditional leader also opposed the Muse Bihi government and used the people against him because they have the right and ability to mobilise and lead their people.

Precipitating cause: The origins of this conflict can be linked to a shift in the international political system, specifically from a unipolar to a multipolar system.

The second cause is a shift in the global political system, and it is not surprising to say that the Lasanod War has been one of the world's political events since 2017, when the US world order began to face potential peer competitors. In other words, the Lasanod War represents a shift in the international political system from a unipolar to a multipolar system, with the decline of US imperialism and the rise of new emerging great powers such as China and Russia.

The Lasanod War is one of the world's political events since 2017, indicating a shift in the international political system. New emerging powers, most notably China, have gradually started to replace the US imperial since 2017, and a foolish US foreign policy towards Russia has compelled Russia to align with China and jointly attempt to establish a new world order. More visible evidence exists to demonstrate that this has occurred and continues to occur on a daily basis in the most important areas of US national geopolitical interests, including the Middle East and the Horn of Africa.

China and Turkey supported the uprising in Ethiopia that gave birth to Dr. Abiy, which ended US influence in the region and welcomed China. The wars between Ethiopia and Tigray, Sudan and Ethiopia, Eritrea and Tigray, Somaliland and Lasanod, and the diplomatic battle between Mr. Mohamed Abdilahi Farmajo, the former president of Somalia, and some Western countries are all the result of a shift in the world political system that shows the removal of the United States from the region. It's also worth noting that Somalia's President Hasan Sheikh's new momentum campaign, in which he is committed to destroying or defeating al-Shabaab, is a battle for US policy which aims to stay in the region.

International political events, particularly in the Middle East, Eastern Europe, and North West Asia, are also demonstrating the ongoing tremors in the US global influence. Russia's invasion of Ukraine, political tensions between Russia and the West, China's strong desire to occupy Taiwan, the Taliban's return to power in Afghanistan, China's new close relationship with the Gulf countries, Iran's influence in the region reaching Iraq, Syria, Yemen, and Lebanon, a new agreement between Iran and Saudi Arabia, two adversaries since 1979, and some countries' desire to trade in their currencies and abandon the dollar (China, Russia, Iran, Saudi Arabia, etc.) are all the result of a shift in the world political system that shows the removal of the

United States from the region. The US's removal of Pakistan's former prime minister, Imran Khan, as well as the planned court case against Imran Khan, are indications of the US's pain in remaining in the region.

The war in Lasanod is the result of Somaliland's relationship with the United States, which is currently vacating the most powerful seat in world politics, and its opposition to China, which is replacing the United States. The most dangerous threat to Somaliland is its close relationship with Twain, an unrecognized country seeking independence from China, the new power that has replaced the United States. This means that the enemies of the United States are involved in the Lasanod War.

When you are a realist political analyst who follows the history of world politics and its changes, as well as the significance of the HOA's geopolitical interests for the great powers, assuming that this is about the cold war between the US and China is very reasonable and predictable. However, there is evidence that China is involved in this matter, one of which is that the Chinese ambassador to Ethiopia met with the majority of the protagonists who led the uprising in the region prior to the start of the war, as Michael Rubin wrote in his article entitled "The White House Will Regret Ignoring Las Anod, Somaliland" in the newspaper AEI, arguing that the war was created rather than started. Again, despite the lack of evidence and reliance on rational theory, Michael Rubin asserted in his article "If China's Push on Somaliland Works, Who Might Be Beijing's Next Target?" published on AEI that China is behind the Lasanod war to punish Somaliland for its recognition of Taiwan.

The ramifications of the HOA's shift in the international political system

The shift in international political leadership has had a significant impact both on the regions of the Middle East and the politics of the Horn of Africa, including Somaliland. This change will remove more of the pro-US or pro-Western governments from those regions, particularly those that are still close to being allies with the United States despite its declining power. These things have already begun. It exemplifies the political transformation that has occurred in Ethiopia, the Horn of Africa's political epicentre. A revolution deposed the TPLF-led government, which had been the US's best friend in the Horn of Africa and Africa. A second great example is the Taliban's return to power in Afghanistan, which the US prevented for 20 years.

Furthermore, the government of President HE. Muse Bihi of Somaliland and HE. Hassan Sheikh of the Somali Faid State will not be able to withstand the effects of the international political system shift, particularly the nationalist Ethiopian political development led by Dr. Abiy Ahmed, unless they devise a new strategy that is to move in the direction of the wind. Somaliland has already seen an example of this problem, with the two-month-long war in Lasanod.

Among the reasons that this is possible are two very important factors: the first is that the challenge of global political governance is between two powers or factions: liberals and nationalists. In other words, Francis Fukuyama's argument about the end of history meant that once the Soviet Union vanished, the world would become a democracy, and thus the world would enter a period of peace and progress. But he overlooked the existence of strong nationalist forces in China and elsewhere around the world.

The war is between the United States and its allies, who want to spread liberal democracy's values and principles to other countries. Each of these countries has its own set of principles and values, and they do not want the liberal democracy that the United States is imposing on them. The war is between those who want to rule beyond their borders (the US imperial and its allies) and interfere in their religion, culture, politics, economy, and every aspect of life, and those who oppose and refuse to interfere in their religion, culture, politics, economy, and own affairs, and their orders to make international political moves (China and Russia). As a result, in every nation that US liberalism has been involved in, there is a strong sense of nationalism. Examples of concrete nationalism include social and religious forces such as ISIL from Iraq to Syria, Alshabab in Somalia, and Boko Haram in Nigeria.

The US and its allies replaced the Soviet Union-backed governments after the Cold War, particularly in Africa and the Middle East, by taking advantage of the absence of the Soviet Union. Ethiopia is an example of a country in the Horn of Africa that the US has established as its closest ally in Africa. In 2001, US foreign policy employed the regime change doctrine to try to topple any regime that it felt resisted or opposed its imperial rule. Those countries included Iraq, Libya, Afghanistan, Syria (Syria resisted), and Iran, and they imposed hard sanctions on Iran.

The US and its allies have intervened in these countries and many others, including African states, and formed governments so they can dictate to them what they want. Every one of those

countries, which was hardly interwoven, has strong nationalism. The social forces that failed in the Arab Spring revolution, such as those in Sudan, Egypt, Morocco, Iraq, Algeria, Lebanon, Jordan, Kuwait, Oman, and Sudan, Djibouti, Mauritania, Palestine, Saudi Arabia, and the Moroccans, were nationalism forces and still exist in those countries. Therefore, the decline of the imperial power of the US will be an opportunity for the forces of nationalism to remove the regime that has close ties with the US.

The second factor that will aid nationalist forces in overthrowing governments supported by the US and its allies is support from new emerging great powers such as China and Russia. The support of China, Russia, and Turkey for the new Ethiopian Prime Minister, Dr. Abiy, who ascended to the throne through the Ethiopian social revolution, is a prime example of this.

The Impact of the Lasanod War and the International Political System Shift on Somaliland

Changes in the international political system have both positive and negative consequences for the world, depending on how nations prepare for the changes in social, political, and economic terms, as well as how much people are aware of the changes. Ethiopia and Eritrea in the HOA, as well as Afghanistan in the Middle East, have benefited from this change. Other countries, including China and Russia, are preparing to benefit from it as well. However, due to poor leadership, national disunity, and selfish and ignorant politicians, the Somali Peninsula is the most vulnerable to its negative influence. Lasanod is one of the symptoms of China and the United States struggle for global dominance in Somaliland, which will have serious consequences for Somaliland and Somalia. Aside from the loss of life, property, and massive displacement caused by the ongoing war in the Lasanod region, the tribal mobilisation in Somaliland for the establishment of a new tribe called Irir Samale to contain the Darood tribe from power is the argliest and worst case scenario.

Lasanod is the start of a wave of wars and chaos in Somaliland, Somalia, Djibouti, and Sudan, and a major war between these countries' armies has already begun in the middle of April 2023. All of the governments, policies, and Western influences in the four countries mentioned will be removed. Nationalist and anti-Western dominance groups will seize power, drawing strength from traditional forces and religion.

Conclusion

The past and present images of Somaliland are diametrically opposed, with the former being of peace, stability, and a vision of a national future. After investigating the international political events that have occurred as a result of the shift in the international political system, it was discovered that the Lasanod conflict is the result of a proxy war between the two great powers: the United States, the declining imperial power, and China and Russia, the emerging great powers. Somaliland's state is always precarious and vulnerable to changes in international politics or the Horn of Africa, which eventually leads to Somaliland's collapse unless the government adopts new strategies and changes its response to the Lasanod crisis and opposition.

As a result, Somaliland's state is always precarious and vulnerable to changes in international politics or the Horn of Africa. Given this, Somaliland has arrived at this period of international political change at a time when the countries that supported Somaliland, the United States, and the West, are losing influence in the global political sphere. Furthermore, Somaliland's foreign policy has been hostile to the emerging great power, China, which is set to replace the US and its allies.

Thus, the Lasanod War is the result of a shift in the international political system. Due to colonial legacies that have affected the relations of the state and society through arbitrary borders, foreign political ideologies (democracy), weak institutions, and middlemen politicians, Somaliland is vulnerable and much more likely to host events like this and even serious conflict than anywhere else in the near future. This will have serious ramifications for Somaliland and the surrounding regions. The decline of the United States' imperial influence in the world and region, as well as the rise of its peer competitors, China and Russia, will lead to all regimes supported by the US being deposed by nationalist and anti-Western intervention forces backed by the new emerging great powers, including China and Russia, and their allies, including Turkey, Iran, Qatar, North Korea, and others. An example is the Ethiopian revolution, which resulted in Dr. Abiy's ascension to power and the outbreak of war with Tigray.

The conflict is the same in Lasanod. China lags behind due to Somaliland's recognition of Taiwan as a sovereign state (China claims it is a part of his country), Somaliland's foreign policy engagement with the US, and the allure of Somaliland's geopolitical location. As a result, if the Somaliland government continues its foolish domestic policy, it addresses the political

climate, including political parties, traditional leaders, mass media, and the enhancement of campaigns for the westernization of Somaliland culture; if it continues its foolish foreign policy against China and in favor of the US, Somaliland will be blown up by the waves of wind and political storms caused by the shift in the international political system.

Recommendation

Lasanod is not only a large mountain of trouble, but one of many such mountains to come. It is a small experimental test that can be used to develop a theory for solving larger problems that will arise in the near future. Furthermore, it is a symptom of a disease that has already affected Somaliland politics, and it should not be examined in isolation; it should be examined in light of the larger picture of the problem as well as any subsequent ones. It is possible that similar conflicts will erupt in other areas such as Hargeisa, Burao, and Borma. As a result, this section describes the underlying cause as well as the initial steps towards a general solution.

Large storms of political conflict are brewing in the region as a result of ongoing changes in international politics. The danger of these political changes will be greater than anywhere else because all countries in the HOA are fragile due to colonial legacies that have influenced the relationship between society and what is known as the modern state, and that it involves a number of issues, four of which are arbitrarily drawn borders, foreign political ideologies, very weak institutions, and political agents (politicians who are representatives of colonialism). As a result, this risk can be addressed in two ways: through adjustment and through perseverance policies.

The adjustment policy is to change the region's old domestic and foreign policies in order to avoid the risk of political conflict. To avoid this risk, old domestic and foreign policies should be changed. In the current situation, the government prefers to stick to its old policies rather than examine the ongoing shift in the international political system. For example, the government of Somaliland has not changed its approach to Lasanod. This is a persistence policy that will not work and will result in failure. These two paths result in two distinct outcomes. If the governments of the Horn, including Somaliland, Somalia, Djibouti, and Sudan, pursue a policy of persistence, they will face national destruction as they face powerful winds and storms that they cannot defeat. They will, however, survive if they make adjustments.

As a result, Somaliland should revise its policy and implement the following measures:

1. In dealing with the Lasanod conflict, the government must abandon its argument that it must protect territorial integrity at all costs and instead engage in dialogue with the opposing side to find a peaceful solution. Additionally, the government should prioritise economic development and job creation to address the root causes of instability in the region.
2. The government of Somaliland must forge new alliances and pivot to the east, particularly with China, Russia, and Ethiopia. These measures will not only benefit Somaliland but also contribute to regional stability and security. It is crucial for the government to take proactive steps toward resolving conflicts and promoting economic growth for the betterment of its citizens.
3. The executive branch of government should be designed in such a way that it cannot interfere with or dominate the legislative and judicial branches. This will ensure a more balanced distribution of power and prevent any abuse of authority. Furthermore, promoting transparency and accountability within the government will help build trust with the citizens and foster a more stable political environment.
4. It should conduct domestic political research and establish an updated and effective foreign policy. By implementing these measures, the government can work towards creating a system that serves the needs of all citizens and promotes the common good. Ultimately, this will lead to a more prosperous and harmonious society for everyone.
5. As all the political instability is due to the delay of the presidential election, the president should disregard the political association elections and instead work to hold the presidential election as soon as possible.
6. Government institutions should be strengthened and relied on rather than relying on a person. Personal judgment in public work should be replaced by institutional judgement in order to socialize people into their best values and principles. This results in a value consensus that allows members of our society to effectively live and work together, and our authorities fulfill their duties in accordance with the will of the society. This means that both citizens and authorities understand how to act and react in most situations in a socially acceptable way based on institutional and constitutional respect.
7. Somaliland's politics should be internalized (away from liberal democracy) while protecting culture, religion, and clan respect.

The Somaliland government is dealing with more than just the Lasanod war; there is also a massive social crisis similar to the Lasanod event that is currently invisible to the government

but may emerge in the near future. Omer I Dhere, one of my colleagues, suggested specific and detailed recommendations that could help to avoid future conflicts. Mr. Omer proposed the followings:

8. First and foremost, the Somaliland government has to reopen negotiations based on the Somaliland-Khaatumo Agreements. As mentioned in the agreements, the Somaliland constitution should be revised and amended to ensure that a fair power sharing based on justice regarding the executive, legislative, and judiciary is implemented. A major component of the agreement is related to the decentralisation of administrative powers, which should be devolved at regional, district, and town levels, and the mandates of each level need to be clarified.
9. Power sharing and decentralisation can be negotiated towards a Somaliland national reconciliation conference. And Somaliland's political landscape was cleaned from the residual clans' politics. The abandonment of blood-based laws for citizen rights calls for shifts in not only mindsets but also to harmonise conflicting laws that regulate all aspects of Somaliland's functions. Customary and Sharia have to be articulated in binding international laws.
10. The National Reconciliation Conference can support a constitutional amendment to adopt the relevant decentralisation policy framework, which empowers local authorities and officials with extended responsibilities in legislative, judicial, and economic development affairs to meet the expectations of local populations. Clear demarcation on various different mandates through an effective power sharing mechanism between Somaliland's national state institutions and those based at regional and district levels will equip Somaliland to significantly achieve unwavering, rock-solid national unity.
11. Decentralised budget policy will authorise each region to prepare, plan, and draught its own genuine budget forecasts that are in line with its regional development objectives and match the local populations' needs. As decentralisation goes hand in hand with the rule of law, forecasting a budget tailored to the regions' exigencies with a development oriented vision A relevant delegation of decision-making power will enhance equal access to all public services.
12. In the event that the Las-Anod issue is not responded to appropriately, it will jeopardise Somaliland's national unity, tarnish the reputation of the Somaliland Republic in the eyes of the whole world, and derail the ongoing Somaliland international recognition process.

Fake news and lies, which are warming the media and social media with unrealistic proportions, will remain unchallenged and will infest negatively public spaces with narratives related to Somaliland's factual sequence of events!

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1. Changing Relations Between Somalia and Ethiopia: Potential Risk on the Horizon, 2019.
2. Somaliland and Ethiopia New Relations: Dr. Abiy's Foreign Policy Towards Somaliland, 2021
3. The Likely Irreversible Catastrophe of Global Warming and Human Ignorance, 2022.
4. Somaliland Minority: .Gaboye Communities' Needs & Living Condition (Assessment), 2022.
5. Destroying the First Ever Hope of the HOA (It is a scholarly article that will be published shortly), 2022

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